

ARCHITECTURE AND ITS MAJESTIC PAINTING ELEMENTS

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Abstract: This article discusses architecture and the use of elements of grandiose painting in it. Also, the elements of the picture are described.

Keywords: art, architecture, color image, element, style, genre.

In recent years, the attention to the tradition and modernity in the harmony of magnificent decorative works with architectural elements is growing in the creative work carried out in our country.

After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the attention paid by the state to cultural heritage and national values, the development of visual arts, history, and spirituality increased. A completely new political basis has emerged in the construction of the state and society of Uzbekistan.

National and universal values were announced as the main value of the new cultural policy. Both of these values gave a unique spirit to modern aesthetic research in the art of Uzbekistan

Also, great attention was paid to freedom of creativity during this period. For the creative development of artists, it has gained huge opportunities. In the territory of Uzbekistan, many directions of fine art developed in the centuries before our era. As an example of the development of monumental decorative art in the territories of ancient Bactria, Khorezm, Sogd, Shosh, wall paintings found during archeological excavations can be cited.

We can observe the influence of monumental works of art on the urban environment on the example of architectural structures built in different parts of our country in the last century.

Majestic works of art have a huge, incomparable impact, are characterized by the grandeur of the subject and its large size. The law of integrity of the composition is especially necessary in the great art, because it is required that the work should be clear and understandable even from a distance. From a distance, small forms are not visible, the number of details is not important for this art, auxiliary details are generalized, and the shape is completely rounded. In the constructive idea of a majestic composition, it is necessary to create a contrast of silhouettes, so that different figures and objects can be recognized from a long distance, and the clarity of the silhouette visible against the background of nature is necessary for the monument.

The basic laws of composition operate according to the essential tasks and conditions of the great art, taking into account the specifics of this art. The specifics of these conditions can be summed up by the fact that majestic art is manifested only when it is filled with architectural and natural environment. Magnificent art was widely developed in ancient Egypt and Ancient Greece. His famous images can also be found in Byzantium (Ravenna monuments) and ancient Russian art (Kiev, Novgorod, Pskov, Vladimir, Moscow).

The talented painter A. Bukhorboyev works in the Florentine mosaic technique. The use of semi-precious stones allows the artwork to be harmoniously connected to the architecture. A three-part composition dedicated to the traditions of the ancient culture of India was created by this artist in the lobby of the hotel "Le Meridien" in Tashkent. Made of white and brown marble, the Central Qiyam is well-received from all points of the interior with clear graphic lines. A. Bukhorboyev uses lapis lazuli, bronze, and jade to depict two women who symbolize Indian craftsmanship.

W. Gan tackled a similar issue while creating a wide spatial composition in the renovation of the current Gems and Minerals Committee Hall of the Asian Bank. These two compositions made of crystal, which are important due to their size, are important in the interior as the main light and compositional accent.

Any structure reflects the traditions of the people who created it, passed down from generation to generation. Monumental works and decoration are considered an integral part of architecture. Functional buildings without decorations have a significant negative impact on the human inner world. Decorations that appear on the surface of buildings visually soften it in the eyes of a person and create positive feelings.

The most important task of monumental art is to transform eternal values into images. This is also how it differs from other types of art. Composition means the organization of aesthetic reality through the systematic arrangement of forms and the location of objects. In visual arts, this reality becomes an image.

Progress has made visual arts the nourishment of the human psyche. Works of art are the fruit of human intelligence and the criterion of development. Every era leaves a mark in history through its science, literature, politics and, of course, art. That is why tradition and modernity are important indicators.

As a conclusion, we can say that the implementation of the above feedback as a process of analysis, study, and research is of particular importance in the development of color image.

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